

Experimental Validation of Correction Factors for In Situ H-Field Measurements below 2 MHz

Jordi Solé-Lloveras^{*#1}, Marco A. Azpúrua^{*#2}, Yasutoshi Yoshioka^{%3}, Ferran Silva^{#4}

^{*}EMC Barcelona, EMC Electromagnetic BCN S.L., Spain

[#]Grup de Compatibilitat Electromagnètica, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Spain

[%]Power System Control Research Department. Digital Innovation Laboratory. Fuji Electric Co., Ltd. Japan

{¹jordi.sole, ²marco.azpuru}@emc-barcelona.com, ³yoshioka-yasutoshi @fujielectric.com

⁴ferran.silva @upc.edu

Abstract—A large number of devices cannot be tested in standard electromagnetic compatibility laboratories due to size, power or safety-related constraints. In these cases, the only viable alternative is the in situ approach. The reference standard for in situ testing, CISPR 11, proposes to evaluate the equipment's emissions in the 150 kHz to 30 MHz range through the measurement of the magnetic field at a 30 m distance. However, at such conditions, the said emissions are barely discernible from ambient noise and sometimes ensuring such fixed measuring distances is not even possible due to limitations of the test site. Emerging standards projects, e.g., CISPR 37, are considering setting the reference distance to 10 m while allowing measures at distances from 3 m to 30 m through the application of specific conversion factors to achieve a result that is comparable to the applicable disturbance limits. In this work, the corresponding magnetic field conversion factors are experimentally studied and validated from the in situ standpoint. Results obtained show an excellent match with the proposal in the latest CISPR 37 draft in the frequency range from 150 kHz to 2 MHz.

Keywords—conversion factors, magnetic field, in situ testing, emissions measurements, standards.

I. INTRODUCTION

All electronic equipment within the European market must comply with the essential requirements of the EMC directive. This covers all types of products, including devices and systems that cannot be tested in standard EMC laboratories due to size, power or safety-related constraints. In these cases, the in situ approach is the only viable alternative.

Only a few standards allow in situ EMC testing. The most widespread is CISPR 11[1], which applies to industrial, scientific and medical devices. In this standard, measurement methods and limits are proposed, both for electric field, above 30 MHz, and for magnetic field, from 150 kHz to 30 MHz. In most EMC standards, frequencies below 30 MHz are usually evaluated through the conducted emission tests. Nevertheless, as there is no clear procedure for performing these measurements under in situ conditions, it is proposed to assess this range through magnetic field measurements. However, in CISPR 11, the reference distance for magnetic

field emissions in situ test is set to 30 m, which might be inconvenient or not even possible in many situations.

The same standard proposes, only for distances greater than 30 m, a conversion factor inversely proportional to the distance. Quoting the standard, “an inverse proportionality factor of 20 dB per decade” can be used. However, two main concerns arise. First, no allowance is made for performing the tests at shorter distances. It is highly likely that the magnetic field strengths from the EUT (Equipment Under Test) emissions are hardly discernible from the ambient noise at distances greater than 30 m. The second problem is whether the far-field condition assumption is valid in order to apply a constant factor of 20 dB per decade. CISPR 11 also provides magnetic field limits at 30 m, 10 m and 3 m, but only for standard test sites.

Also, there are other standards, for instance CISPR 16-2-3 [2], and technical reports like CISPR 16-2-5 [3] where in situ test procedures are mentioned, but they do not specify distance conversion factors for frequencies below 30 MHz.

Currently, CISPR 37 [4], a standard project focusing on in situ testing, is being developed by CIS/B WG7. In the latest draft, simulation-based distance conversion factors for magnetic field emissions are proposed in a table, including measurement distances from 3 m to 100 m. For such discrete distances, a frequency-dependent “extrapolation factor” is given in decibel units. The said factor function is defined piece-wise, with a first interval expressed as a constant factor from 150 kHz up to f_1 , a second segment in the form of a log-linear fit from f_1 to f_2 and a third range which is again a constant factor from f_2 until 30 MHz. The corner frequencies, f_1 and f_2 , vary depending on the distance and are specified in the same table. Then, for other measurement distances not included in the same table, the corresponding factor are interpolated.

Even though the need for distance correction factors is evident in the context of H-field emissions measurement, their general validity remains unclear. To address those concerns, this study investigates the magnetic field distance correction factors from 150 kHz to 30 MHz in the range from 3 m up to 30 m. The intention is to empirically obtain such factors in a realistic environment and check whether the proposal in the CISPR 37 draft matches the experiment results, while

This work was supported in part by the project 21NRM06 EMC-STD which has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme.

establishing a relationship between such factors and the limits defined for H-field measurements at fixed distances given in CISPR 11. To carry out the study, two transmitting loops were built to generate a magnetic field from an injected signal. The reason for constructing two loops is to check if there is any noticeable difference when the size of the equipment varies. Subsequently, a known signal will be injected on the transmitting loops while a 60 cm loop antenna according to CISPR 16-1-4 will be used to measure the magnetic field magnitude on the x -, y - and z -axes for different measuring distances, thus studying the behavior of the transmission of the H-field as a function of distance and frequency.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Design and manufacture of the loops

Two square loops are built in order to generate magnetic field in a repeatable and straightforward manner. The construction layout of both loops is depicted in Fig. 1. The big loop, Loop A, is constructed with a dimension of $1.5\text{ m} \times 1.5\text{ m}$. Subsequently, Loop B, has half of the side size of Loop A, with a dimension of $0.75\text{ m} \times 0.75\text{ m}$. The center of both loops coincide and is $h = 1.25\text{ m}$. The two loops have different sizes in order to compare how this effect impacts the magnetic field emission at different frequencies.

Fig. 1. Design layout for the transmitting H-field loops.

PVC pipe is used for the structure, and an unshielded Ethernet cable (Cat 6 UTP) is used as the inner conductor. A homemade coupling network based on CISPR 32 is used to feed the loop. It consists of a serial RC network with $R = 100\ \Omega$ and $C = 2.2\text{ nF}$, connecting all the Ethernet wires to a common feeding point (Fig. 2). The Ethernet cables run twisted 1.5 m from the middle point of the bottom pipe to the coupling network (CN). The other end is connected through a coaxial cable to the signal generator.

Fig. 2. Design layout for the transmitting H-field loops.

Fig. 3. Proposed experiment.

Fig. 4. Defined antenna axes: (a) x ; (b) y ; (c) z .

B. Experiment

The transmitting loop is placed at a measurement distance, d , from a broadband active loop antenna Rohde & Schwarz HFH2-Z2E (Fig. 3). Then, the transmitting loop is connected to the CN output and the CN input is fed by an arbitrary waveform generator. On the measurement end, the receiving antenna is connected to a time domain measuring receiver.

The transmitting loop is kept normal to the x -axis, while the measuring antenna is oriented in three orthogonal axes. The defined axes of the antenna are depicted in Fig. 4. The height of the measuring antenna from the ground to the center of the loop is $h = 125\text{ cm}$.

Several distances are evaluated on an open site in order to study the transmission of the magnetic field. The transmitting antenna is placed in the following distances from the measuring antenna: 3 m, 4 m, 5 m, 6 m, 7 m, 8 m, 9 m, 10 m, 12 m, 15 m, 20 m, 25 m and 30 m. The measuring antenna is fixed in the same position in order to keep an ambient noise level as similar and repetitive as possible in all measurements. No obstacle was closer than 5 m of any of the loops at the respective positions. The experiment at a distance $d = 3\text{ m}$ for Loop B can be observed in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Example case with $d = 3\text{ m}$ and Loop B.

C. Injected signal

In order to obtain the transmission characteristic between the two antennas in the complete range from 9 kHz to 30 MHz chirp signals are used. The first chirp has an initial frequency of 9 kHz and a final frequency of 11 MHz in logarithmic steps. Second chirp has an initial frequency of 2 MHz and a final frequency of 30 MHz in linear steps. Both chirps have a sweep time of 1 s and are unidirectional. Although the experiment is set from 150 kHz, it is interesting to have data available from lower frequencies for future studies. To cover the whole frequency range, spectrum of both chirps must be combined. This is done by using the spectrum of the first chirp from 9 kHz to 2.5 MHz and the spectrum of the second chirp from 2.5 MHz to 30 MHz.

The chirp voltage exhibits a flat frequency response from 9 kHz to 30 MHz. However, when applied to the coupling network connected to the loop, a resonance is observed due to the loop's self inductance. Results of the measured current in differential mode for both loops are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Spectrum of the current measured in differential mode for the signal injected in Loop A and Loop B.

D. Measurement system

The full cycle of the injected signal must be measured in a single acquisition, guaranteeing a common ambient noise condition for the whole spectrum. This aspect is fundamental in many types of measurements, but especially when performing in situ tests or measures of complex systems, where the ambient noise may vary in time and the equipment may have rapidly changing operating modes. For such scenarios, including the experiment in this study, a typical frequency-swept receiver is not suitable [5], [6], [7].

Therefore, a custom time-domain measurement system (emiGO) was employed to perform the experiment. This system is based on a general-purpose oscilloscope (Picoscope 5444D MSO) connected to a computer with the software that computes the spectrum in compliance with existing standards. The measurement parameters are the following: resolution bandwidth of 9 kHz, sampling rate of 250 MSa/s, vertical resolution of 12 bit and measurement time of 1 s.

III. RESULTS

A. Magnetic field vs distance

Only the results for x - and z - axes are presented as the y -axis component of the field is very weak. H-Field vector in

Fig. 7. H-Field as a function of distance for Loop A in the x -axis.

Fig. 8. H-Field as a function of distance for Loop A in the z -axis.

y direction is almost negligible because of the orthogonality of the transmitting and measuring antennas planes. Regarding the z component, it is mainly influenced by the characteristics of the ground surface.

Received magnetic field as a function of distance is shown for Loop A in the x - and z - axes in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 respectively. Ambient noise (marked in the legend as 'N') is also depicted. The ambient noise is practically identical in all measurements because the receiving antennas was kept in the same position. No significant variations of the ambient noise were noticed during the experiment.

A higher ambient noise level is present on the x -axis compared to the z -axis. The ambient noise level will limit the maximum usable distance of the experiment, since eventually there will be a point at which no useful signal is detectable. As expected, received signal level in the x -axis is also higher than in the z -axis. In both graphs, a progressive decay of the magnetic field level as a function of distance is seen from 30 kHz to 2 MHz. In this same frequency range, for distances greater than 20 m in the x -axis and distances greater than 15 m for the z -axis, the ambient noise dominates and the useful signal is below the noise. This is important to be taken into account, because measurements at distances greater than these

cannot be used to draw any conclusions.

Above 2 MHz and up to 30 MHz, the level of magnetic field at all distances is very similar. Therefore, it was found that in this frequency range other unknown dominant effect or source is present (for example coupling between the generator and measuring system). In consequence, the experiment is not conclusive in such frequency range. Below 2 MHz, the behaviour is stable, so, a frequency where there is no strong ambient noise is selected to use it as a reference. For the studied cases, this frequency is $f = 400$ kHz.

Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 show the results for Loop B at x - and z -axes respectively. According to the radiation characteristics of a small loop [8], the field strengths are proportional to the loop area, so decreasing the area 4 times would yield to a difference in the magnetic field level of -12.04 dB. For x -axis, the measured difference at $f = 400$ kHz is -10.42 dB. Such variation between the experimental and theoretical values might be explained by antenna losses, impedance mismatches and parasitic effects. However, this discrepancy is not of a major importance in the experiment since the main goal is to obtain relative factors.

Fig. 9. H-Field as a function of distance for Loop B in the x -axis.

Fig. 10. H-Field as a function of distance for Loop B in the z -axis.

For Loop B, similar behaviour as Loop A is observed, but with a lower magnetic field level. The usable distance is

reduced regarding the former case.

B. Current to H-Field conversion factor

Another interesting approach to analyze the results is to study the conversion factor between the current injected in the transmitting loop and the magnetic field sensed at the measuring antenna, which will depend on the distance:

$$CF[\text{dBm}^{-1}] = H_{meas}[\text{dBuA/m}] - I_{DM}[\text{dBuA}], \quad (1)$$

where CF is the conversion factor, H_{meas} is the measured H-field strength and I_{DM} is the injected current in the loop. For Loop A, data from x and z axes is shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 respectively. Data is shown only for the frequency range where the previous experiment was valid (100 kHz - 2 MHz).

Fig. 11. H-Field normalized to injected current for Loop A and x -axis.

Fig. 12. H-Field normalized to injected current for Loop A and z -axis.

A meaningful conversion factor is only calculable for frequencies at which ambient noise is low with respect to generated field levels.

For Loop B, data from x and z axes is shown in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 respectively.

A linear relation between injected current and magnetic field strength is observed even though we are in near-field conditions for some distances.

Fig. 13. H-Field normalized to injected current for Loop B and x -axis.

Fig. 14. H-Field normalized to injected current for Loop B and z -axis.

C. Normalized H-Field to 3 m

In order to convert the magnetic field level obtained in an in situ measurement campaign, normalized factors are needed for a reference distance. Typically, the distance where the measurements are normalized is the distance requested by the limit in the corresponding standard, e.g. 3 m, 10 m or 30 m. In what follows, the reference distance is set to 3 m. One advantage of measuring at a short distance is that the emissions produced by the EUT can be observed with a higher level with respect to the ambient noise. Moreover, as it was commented, in the frequency range where we wish to measure there is a linear relation between injected current and magnetic field strength.

In Tables 1 and 2 we show the conversion factors normalized to 3 m, for a measuring distance, d , calculated from for Loops A and B, $C_A(d)$ and $C_B(d)$, respectively. Also, it is shown the CISPR 37 factors normalized to 3 m, $C_S(d)$, in order to facilitate the verification. Finally, two comparison rows, $\Delta_A(d)$ and $\Delta_B(d)$ which show to the difference between $C_S(d)$ and the experimental conversion factors $C_A(d)$ and $C_B(d)$. The results are given for a measurement frequency of $f = 400$ kHz. The absolute magnitude values of the magnetic field at 3 m are the following: $H_{A,X} = 62.52$ dB μ A/m,

$H_{A,Z} = 48.25$ dB μ A/m, $H_{B,X} = 53.16$ dB μ A/m. $H_{B,Z} = 35.17$ dB μ A/m. All factors are derived from these values.

The values in red imply that the measured magnetic field strength is below ambient level, therefore no valid factors can be extracted from the experiments performed.

Table 1. Comparison table for x -axis.

d [m]	C_A [dB]	C_B [dB]	C_S [dB]	Δ_A [dB]	Δ_B [dB]
3	0	0	0	0	0
4	-5.78	-6.8	-6.2	-0.42	0.6
5	-10.7	-12.08	-11	-0.3	1.08
6	-14.81	-16.3	-14.8	0.01	1.5
7	-18.39	-19.45	-18.4	-0.01	1.05
8	-21.74	-22.77	-21.4	0.34	1.37
9	-24.42	-25.57	-24.2	0.22	1.37
10	-26.67	-27.35	-26.7	-0.03	0.65
12	-31.37	-31.41	-31.1	0.27	0.31
15	-37.03	-35.4	-36.5	0.53	-1.1
20	-40.72	-40.29	-43.7	-2.98	-3.41
25	-47.86	42.14	-49.2	-1.34	-7.06
30	-48.13	-41.04	-53.9	-5.77	-12.86

Table 2. Comparison table for z -axis.

d [m]	C_A [dB]	C_B [dB]	C_S [dB]	Δ_A [dB]	Δ_B [dB]
3	0	0	0	0	0
4	-3.97	-4.07	-6.2	-2.23	-2.13
5	-10.11	-8.93	-11	-0.89	-2.07
6	-13.32	-13.39	-14.8	-1.48	-1.41
7	-18.09	-16.82	-18.4	-0.31	-1.58
8	-20.84	-20.76	-21.4	-0.56	-0.64
9	-24.22	-23.37	-24.2	0.02	-0.83
10	-27.27	-25.32	-26.7	0.57	-1.38
12	-30.92	-27.89	-31.1	-0.18	-3.21
15	-35.63	-30.59	-36.5	-0.87	-5.91
20	-40.17	-30.87	-43.7	-3.53	-12.83
25	-42.1	-31	-49.2	-7.1	-18.2
30	-40.29	-30.55	-53.9	-13.61	-23.35

$C_A(d)$ and $C_B(d)$ for x and z axes are plotted in Fig. 15 and Fig. 16 respectively. Note that the distance is in logarithmic scale. The factors for the same axis for both loops are overlapped, as well as the factors proposed by CISPR 37. A log-linear model is generated and displayed on the plots. To fit the model, items marked in red in the preceding tables are considered as outliers.

Fig. 15. Conversion factors for Loop A and B. x -axis.

An excellent match can be observed between the factors obtained and those proposed in CISPR 37. The model (straight and dashed line) does match the proposed factors.

Fig. 16. Conversion factors for Loop A and B. z -axis.

In the case of the z -axis, there is a larger discrepancy due to the lower level of magnetic field measured as well as the ground predominant in this axis.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Regarding the distance conversion factors, the experiment delivered excellent results in the range from 150 kHz to 2 MHz. However, the experiment should be improved to cover the frequency range from 2 MHz to 30 MHz. Given the good correspondence between experiments below 2 MHz and the factor provided by CISPR 37, which are based on simulation, it may indicate that the CISPR 37 factors will also be valid for higher frequencies.

Another interesting approach is the definition of the measurement distance for the disturbance limits for in situ tests. As mentioned above, the currently valid measurement distance is 30 m according to CISPR 11. Furthermore, there is no possible method to evaluate shorter distances in terms of magnetic field. At such large distances, the limits are very restrictive in terms of ambient noise, and unless the equipment emits with very high power, the EUT emissions are difficult to distinguish from the ambient noise. Therefore, it is proposed either to define limits at 3 m or 10 m, or to provide conversion factors for such distances. As there is no evident field deformation at 3 m even at low frequencies, it would be interesting to use a reference distance of 3 m in order to have a greater ratio between the equipment emissions and the ambient noise.

Concerning the methodology, it has been found that keeping the measurement antenna in a fixed position and moving the emission source can be advantageous, since the ambient noise remains much more constant. It is also observed that changing the area of the transmitting loop does not produce significant differences in the calculated distance conversion factors.

A collateral observation is that it is important to take into account the location of surrounding cables connection the emission sources, since the effect provoked by such items might be more relevant than the intended EUT or source itself. This is important when conducting in situ tests. Moreover, although it is out of the scope of this study, ground might have an important impact during the tests.

Finally, this work helps understanding the applicability of new magnetic field emission limits and distance conversion factors for in situ conditions, as it provides empirical evidence to validate and build consensus between existing standards towards the models used to defined them.

To summarize, very good results have been obtained from 150 kHz to 2 MHz, which justify the feasibility of conducting in situ magnetic field measurements at distances much shorter than those currently proposed in the current standards. It is still necessary to evaluate the conversion factors from 2 MHz to 30 MHz.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the “Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación” of Spain through the Project DIN2021-012003 under Grant MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and Project PID2019-106120RBC31/AEI/10.13039/501100011033.

REFERENCES

- [1] CISPR 11:2015 - *Industrial, Scientific and Medical Equipment - Radio-Frequency Disturbance Characteristics - Limits and Methods of Measurement*, Geneva, Switzerland, 2015.
- [2] CISPR 16-2-3: *Specification for Radio Disturbance and Immunity Measuring Apparatus and Methods - Part 2-3: Methods of Measurement of Disturbances and Immunity - Radiated Disturbance Measurements*, Geneva, Switzerland, 2016.
- [3] CISPR TR 16-2-5: *Specification for Radio Disturbance and Immunity Measuring Apparatus and Methods - Part 2-5: In Situ Measurements for Disturbing Emissions Produced by Physically Large Equipment*, Geneva, Switzerland, 2007.
- [4] CISPR 37: *Industrial, Scientific and Medical Equipment - Radio-Frequency Disturbance Characteristics - Limits and Methods for Measurements In Situ - CD 2*, 2022.
- [5] J. Solé-Lloveras, M. A. Azpúrua, Y. Yoshioka, and F. Silva, “Strategies using time-domain measurements for radiated emissions testing in harsh environments,” *IEEE Open Journal of Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 2, pp. 1–11, 2023.
- [6] J. Solé-Lloveras, M. A. Azpúrua, M. Aragn Homar, Y. Yoshioka, and F. Silva, “Efficient in situ assessment of radiated emissions using time-domain measurements,” in *2023 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility - EMC Europe*, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [7] M. A. Azpúrua, J. Solé-Lloveras, R. Marthinsen, and F. Silva, “Rapid emission check of photovoltaic installations using time domain measurements,” *IEEE Electromagnetic Compatibility Magazine*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 73–78, 2023.
- [8] C. A. Balanis, “Loop antennas,” in *Antenna theory: analysis and design*. John Wiley & Sons, 2016, ch. 5.